

THE GOALS AND TASKS OF DEVELOPING CREATIVE THINKING ABILITIES OF PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Any person wants to perceive the world around him and understand it. To understand means to realize the essence of an object and phenomenon, as well as to see the most necessary things in them. We can say that understanding is the most complex cognitive psychological process called thinking. Before moving on to considering the creative thinking of children of primary school age, let us define what thinking is as a psychological process in general.

First of all, we note that thinking is the highest cognitive process. Thinking refers to the acquisition of completely new knowledge and the creative transformation of those ideas and knowledge that already exist. In addition, thinking should be understood as the acquisition of completely new knowledge acquired by a person [1]. Thinking as a special mental process has a number of specific characteristics and features. The first such sign is a generalized reflection of reality. The second, no less important, is the indirect knowledge of objective reality. The next most important characteristic feature of thinking is that thinking is almost always associated with the solution of one or another problem that arises in the process of cognition or in practical activity. Thinking always begins with a question, the answer to which is the goal of thinking. Moreover, the answer to this question is not found immediately, but with the help of certain mental operations.

One of the more significant signs of the revolution in education can be considered the transition from the assimilation of information to the formation of qualities necessary for creative activity and the constant assimilation of new information, as well as the establishment of a competency-based approach to constructing the content of education, in which learning outcomes are important. Creative competence can be defined as supra-subject or core. Key competencies must be favorable for all members of society, that is, appropriate for everyone, regardless of gender, race, marital status, etc. They must correspond to the goals of education and be personally oriented [3]. Competence in creative activity involves identifying the creative potential of students, logical, imaginative thinking, and creating conditions for the development of a creative

personality. The teacher's activities should be aimed at stimulating students' creativity, conducting lessons, and organizing students' research work.

The main principles of work in the development of creative thinking abilities in junior schoolchildren are:

- conditioning of education by social needs and living conditions;

- interdependence of upbringing, training, education and personal development;

- dependence of education on the age and individual characteristics of the student.

Creative thinking is not always associated with one type of thinking. Psychologists have spent a large amount of time and effort trying to figure out how a person finds solutions to new, completely unusual problems. Until now, there is no clear answer to the question about the psychological nature of creativity. Psychology has only some data that makes it possible to describe the process of solving problems and characterize the conditions that contribute to finding an exact solution. The main feature of creative thinking is the ability not only to analyze problems that have arisen, but also to establish systemic relationships [1].

To solve the problem of developing creative thinking, the primary school age deserves special attention, when the foundations for further personal development are laid. At this age, children demonstrate high cognitive creative

activity, expressing their impressions, experiences, feelings, and ideas about the world as a whole in the results of creative activity. Teachers are faced with an important task - to educate a creative person whose activities would be purposeful and constructive in nature. The developing personality should be the focus of all extracurricular activities in the classroom. It is possible to successfully implement an integrated approach in the process of developing the creative thinking of younger schoolchildren within the framework of extracurricular activities if the following conditions are met:

- dominance of the developmental capabilities of educational material over its information richness;
- combination of the conditions for the development of productive thinking with the skills of its practical use;
- dominance of one's own research practice over reproductive assimilation of knowledge, etc. [2].

In order to develop in students, the ability to creatively solve educational problems, it is necessary, first of all, to take care of developing their horizons, of creating a real sensory basis for imagination. Thus, an analysis of psychological literature has shown that most domestic psychologists consider the concepts of "creativity" without distinguishing them with the concepts of "creative thinking". The relevance of the problem of developing the creative activity of primary school students, their abilities to complete educational tasks of varying complexity, perseverance and independence is justified. All this requires the creation of conditions that would contribute to the formation and development of creative personality traits in students. In this regard, the effectiveness of an educational institution is determined by how the educational process ensures the development of students' creative abilities and prepares them for social life. Analyzing the above, we came to the conclusion that the optimal structure for presenting educational material for the purpose of developing creative abilities will be a combination of traditional presentation with the inclusion of problem situations. The formulation of a problem situation makes it possible to make learning activities more attractive for students, based on constant difficulties, leads to the emergence of a cognitive need, and therefore, the student's mental activity increases and intelligence and creative thinking develop. The process of using problem situations in teaching primary schoolchildren as a means of developing creative thinking is a difficult process, since this process is an individual act. Therefore, the teacher is required to make maximum use of all those resources that are hidden in the content of the initial education course,

differentiated and individual approaches and effective methodological techniques.

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